

SCANCLOUDT – A NEW PROJECT TO IMPROVE TRACEABILITY FOR INDUSTRIAL 3D DIGITALIZATION BY ADVANCED SCANNING SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

3D laser scanning systems are vital for the digital transformation of macroscopic geometric surface [1] measurements. However, current metrological tools lag 3D laser scanning systems' technical advances. In addition, assessing the measurement uncertainty of 3D laser scanning systems requires unrealistic computation effort. In addition, assessing the measurement uncertainty of 3D laser scanning systems requires unrealistic computation efforts. To find a viable but metrologically valid solution to this challenge for dimensional metrology, eight European National Metrology institutes have teamed up with seven academic and industrial partners in the '24DIT04 ScanCloudT' project. This project will address these metrological issues by developing new approaches for the entire data capture and point cloud processing chain. New, validated digital metrological twins (D-MTs) will be developed which will be used to assess the complete physical measurement. A holistic quality metric will also be derived to handle the typical, excessively large point clouds. Further to this, verification strategies will be developed to validate dedicated software packages, as well as case studies in aerospace manufacturing, logistics and geodesy which will be used to demonstrate the potential of the project's developed methods.

INTRODUCTION

3D laser scanning systems are vital for the digital transformation of geometric surface measurements also in large volume metrology. 3D laser scanning data acquisition can be well integrated and fully automated into industrial workflows. Already today, systems are widely used commercially, for example in mechanical engineering, construction, infrastructure capture and cargo logistics. In manufacturing, 3D scanning systems are used for prototyping, quality control, or reverse engineering. They considerably simplify and vastly speed up the capture of non-trivial geometries or features that are difficult to access with point probes. As an example, 3D scanning can be a key technology for the surface characterization and structural testing of new aircraft designs with aerostructures made of lightweight composite material. Figure 1 shows a high-quality scan of a 2.5 m wide antenna surface acquired with a new optical 3D scanning system [2]. In the construction sector, 3D scanning enables efficient capture and

FIGURE 1. Cloud-to-mesh (C2M) signed distance map of a 2.5 m wide antenna surface with respect to a fitted paraboloid, measured from 7 m distance. Deviations range from -1.8 mm (blue) to $+2.6$ mm (red) acquired with a new type of 3D scanner introduced in [1].

surface digitization of building stock at city scale volumes. The use of 3D scanners is an established and integral part of this sector. Beyond current recording for Building Information Modelling, improved understanding of uncertainties and standardized digital workflows are needed for more critical applications. Monitoring Europe's transportation and building infrastructure is a key challenge in the EU, as both demand and engineering requirements for inspection, evaluation and management have increased over the last few years, especially for bridges and tunnels. 3D laser scanning is well suited to accelerate the digitalization of monitoring tasks [3]. In logistics, 3D scanning data of cargo enables dimensioning of irregularly shaped items which is essential for the optimization of loading and packing. Furthermore, 3D scanning data is often the basis for cost estimation and pricing in this sector. However, the influence of various materials in logistics (cardboard packaging, wood, or colored shrink wrap) with different absorption properties pose major challenges for optical 3D surface measurement. Furthermore, 3D scanning data is often the basis for cost estimation and pricing in this sector. However, the influence of various materials in logistics (cardboard packaging, wood, or colored shrink wrap) with different absorption properties pose major challenges for optical 3D surface measurement. However, the influence of various materials in logistics (cardboard packaging, wood, or colored shrink wrap) with different absorption properties poses major challenges for 3D scanning measurements.

FIGURE 2. Contributions to the geometrically interpretable measurement result from a laser scanning-based measurement

Assessing the uncertainty of a measurement performed with a 3D laser scanning system is far from trivial. Figure 2 summarizes the major steps in the complex process chain from data capture to final measurement result. Compared to classical dimensional measurements, the primary output from object surface scanning systems are no more than large numbers of 3D coordinate data points whose individual measurement uncertainty is, in general, considered to be worse than that of more classical approaches. The uncertainty of the individual data point depends on the instrument, environmental influences and the interaction between light and the surface of the material being measured. The situation is particularly challenging when laser scanning non-cooperative targets which have specular reflectivity and / or transparency at the wavelength of the scanning laser beam. Post-processing is often carried out using proprietary or at least complex software packages adding further to uncertainty contributions. The large individual scan datasets require registration which can lead to scale distortions in the data fusion process. Finally, the geometric characteristic in question is typically extracted from the point cloud by fitting geometric primitives such as spheres, planes and lines, or complete surface descriptions based on mathematical models. Large volumes of data combined with the non-linearity of the analysis chain pose severe challenges in terms of computation costs and time when applying the classical approach to measurement uncertainty assessment based on forward uncertainty propagation. Alternative more practical metrologically sound approaches to assess the measurement uncertainty of a geometric measurement based on 3D laser scanning are desperately needed.

The ScanClouDT project

To find a viable but metrologically valid solution to this challenge for dimensional metrology, eight European National Metrology institutes teamed up with seven academic and industrial partners

are working together in the '24DIT04 ScanClouDT' project. Commencing on June 1st, 2025, the project is designed to tackle all aspects of the processing chain sketched in Figure 2. The project structure with its work packages (WPs) as discussed below is depicted in Figure 3.

WP1 DM-Ts and virtual experiments

Assessment of the uncertainty of the 3D laser scanner instrument is highly complex. There are two ASTM standards (ASTM E2938-15 and ASTM E3124-17) [4, 5] and one ISO field test (ISO 17123-9) [6] to verify volumetric performance of TLS systems. Mulikrishnan and co-workers published a model for instrumental errors of terrestrial laser scanners (TLS) in 2015 with 18 parameters [7, 8]. Both, a-priori and in-situ calibration strategies have been pursued. However, derived error compensation strategies have shown limited agreement when making systematic comparisons (e.g. [9]). Further to this, the strong influence of the optical properties of the sample surfaces on the achievable measurement uncertainty significantly questions the transferability of characterization methods based on optically compliment surfaces to the achievable measurement uncertainty.

For similarly complex measurement scenarios, e.g. in the case of coordinate measurement machines, virtual experiments based on digital metrological twins (D-MTs) have proven their capability to investigate the measurement uncertainty [10-12]. Various platforms for virtual scanning experiments have been developed since the advent of early scanners [13-18]. Their objective is efficient planning and simulation of different measurement strategies, as well as education and training. ScanClouDT plans to develop D-MTs of selected polar 3D laser scanning systems used in industrial manufacturing, logistics and geodesy. Functional or descriptive models of all relevant physical and technical aspects will be systematically developed as discrete modules. Deviations from

FIGURE 3. Technical work packages (WPs) of the ScanClouDT project.

the optimum design or ideal environmental conditions will be parametrized in a manner that is accessible to the user. The D-MTs will also cover the complete measurement process, especially models for surface-probe optical interactions, using material samples relevant for project case studies in industrial manufacturing, logistics and geodesy. All input model parameters will be determined with traceability to the SI-definition of the meter and the analysis will include their measurement uncertainty. Representative sets of point clouds will be generated for a specific measurement process which follow the requirements of GUM Supplement 1 [19]. As a result, the project's D-MT approach will enable (1) the GUM-conformal propagation of uncertainty contributions to the point cloud product, (2) the study of the relevance of specific uncertainty contributions and (3) realistic simulations and thus, realistic optimization strategies.

WP2 Point cloud quality

Point clouds are an intermediate product between physical measurement and feature measurement. Multiple quality assessment strategies have been proposed, but these are strongly dependent on the application field. In metrology, the dominating philosophy is to link the point cloud assessment to the instrument used. Existing standards such as ASTM E3125-17 [20] or ISO 10360-13 [21] describe acceptance and verification tests using SI-traceable artifacts. However, attempts to classically propagate the measurement uncertainty led to unwieldy covariance-variance matrices with million times millions of entries for scanning data. The ScanClouDT project intends

to develop a holistic characterization method for the point clouds that are used for applications in the field of dimensional metrology based on metadata such as scale distortions, surface planarity, or repeatability. This metric will allow an approximate, yet metrology-grade assessment of point cloud measurement uncertainty, which will be as independent from the details of the original scanning experiment as possible. Extensive measurement comparisons with 3D scanning systems and D-MTs using a variety of measurement standards with typical dimensions, features and materials generated instruments will be performed for the development of such a metric in the ScanClouDT project as well.

WP3 Fusion/registration software validation

Proprietary software packages enable users to perform automated 3D reconstruction and fusion. Nonetheless, for many software solutions, performance in terms of computational costs is the prime target followed closely by (end user) visual impression, while stability and robustness of 3D scanning errors may be of lesser concern and need independent validation. Stability means that the underlying numerical operations are numerically stable, while robustness refers to the software's ability to handle extreme cases, for example systematic bias due to laser reflections when scanning cylindrical holes. Currently, established software tests in coordinate metrology are based on small datasets with simple geometric features and a limited number of data points. However, these tests do not sufficiently cover the challenges of a laser scanner generated 3D point cloud evaluation, such as where the surfaces being captured are not Lambertian in their reflectance. Two

approaches will be pursued by the ScanCloudT project to develop reference datasets for the metrological verification of point cloud processing software packages. Procedures will be developed to generate empirical reference datasets from experimental data generated using dedicated artifacts and high-quality scanning systems. Independent knowledge of the ground truth, for example from tactile probing systems, should allow an evaluation of completeness and accuracy of respective software analyses. The focus, however, will be on the development of a validated numerical generator of qualified reference data for huge 3D datasets. Datasets will comprise (i) classical geometries such as spheres, planes, cylinders and (ii) more complex geometries that are typical for two or more applications. Their application to proprietary software packages will be verified in the project as well.

WP4 Case studies

The stringent determination of the GUM-conformal measurement uncertainty by D-MT application, point cloud assessment and feature derivation by validated software developed in the project will be applied and explained through worked examples based on specific problems in three case studies covering a geodetic network, SI-traceable verification of logistics measurements and a demonstrator for aerospace applications.

CONCLUSIONS

3D laser scanning is evolving across many large volume surface recording applications from a tool for fast and efficient documentation and visualization to a measurement tool applied for more critical measurements. A practical, yet GUM-conformal assessment of the measurement uncertainty is still missing. The freshly-started European ScanCloudT project explores new approaches along the complete measurement processing chain to deliver practical, metrologically sound solutions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The project 24DIT04 ScanCloudT has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

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